

Ensure that double quotes (") are properly escaped as (\"), and remove any line breaks before use, as the prompt in this document was formatted for readability.

Prompt:

role: system

You are an assistant who generates detailed IoT system scenarios from a use case. Your response should only contain a JSON containing all the scenarios found.

role: user

Your job is to find all possible scenarios from the following IoT system use case. This means that you must find all possible execution branches in the following IoT system use case. The following use case is structured similarly to RUCM but as a JSON and adapted to IoT systems :

<Insert Use Case Here>

The information of all steps must be conserved and intact in the created scenarios. You must also add a new stepType field for each step that indicates the type of scenario step. The possible types of scenario steps are INPUT, CONDITION, OUTPUT and STEP. Input steps represent the request or sending of data between components of the system, they can generally be identified from the presence of the fields protocol, method, operation, component and inputs.

Output steps represent the response or confirmation of action taken generally in response to an input, they can generally be identified from the presence of the field outputs.

Condition steps represent the steps that evaluate the conditions for alternate branching, they can be identified by the presence of one or multiple alternate flows pointing to it. Normal steps are simply any other steps and should be simply identified as STEP.

You can (and often should) add JSON array field rules in the condition steps that describe the data constraints to follow the current scenario using the property notation of JSON schema. The name of the scenario describes in general what happens in it.

Make sure to enter all the scenarios found in a JSON that respects this JSON schema :

```
{
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "Scenarios": {
      "type": "array",
      "items": {
```

```
"type": "object",
"properties": {
  "Name": {
    "type": "string"
  },
  "Steps": {
    "type": "array",
    "items": {
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "content": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "stepType": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "protocol": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "method": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "component": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "operation": {
          "type": "string"
        },
        "inputs": {
          "type": "array",
          "items": {
            "type": "string"
          }
        },
        "rules": {
          "type": "array",
          "items": {
            "type": "string"
          }
        },
        "outputs": {
          "type": "array",
          "items": {
            "type": "string"
          }
        }
      }
    },
  "required": [
```

```
"content",
"stepType"
]
}
},
"required": [
"Name",
"Steps"
]
}
},
"required": [
"Scenarios"
]
}
```

Also make sure you answer with nothing else but the JSON you created (that contains the scenarios) as your response will be parsed automatically (don't even put a markdown code block).

Three last things: 1. I repeat that the JSON schema included in this prompt is not what I want as a result and is simply an indication of the JSON structure to follow. 2. Be sure to give exhaustive coverage of the possible scenarios. 3. Make sure to return a valid JSON.